

Academic Education

What bachelor's degree are you studying for?

How many years of study does it take to earn your degree?

Select the requirements engineering topics that you studied before enrolling for this UPM master's programme;

- Elicitation techniques
- Natural language analysis
- Data modelling
- Process modelling
- Use cases / user stories
- Requirements writing
- Requirements tools
- Reviews
- Mock-ups / storyboards / prototyping
- Change management
- Formal specification
- Model checking
- Product lines
- Others

If you have checked "others", please specify further:

Have you ever attended a course or seminar on requirements elicitation?

- Never
- As part of my bachelor's programme
- A specialized seminar

Have you completed assignments or practical exercises on requirements elicitation?

- Never
- As part of my bachelor's programme
- A specialized seminar

Professional Experience

Are you currently:

- Studying?
- Working?
- Studying and working?

If you are working, specify your position:

Specify previous positions you have held (if any):

Have you participated in a real project as an analyst? How many times?

How many years of interviewing experience do you have? (If you are not sure, give an approximate number; numbers may contain decimals)

How many years of elicitation experience do you have? (If you are not sure, give an approximate number; numbers may contain decimals)

Rate your skills in (from 1= very low and 5 = very high):

SKILL	1	2	3	4	5
Interviews					
Requirements Specification					

Knowledge of the problem domain

Rate your knowledge of the problem stated in the exercises?

PROBLEM	1	2	3
AP1			
IP1			
1. It is the first time you have dealt with this type of problem 2. The problem is familiar to you but you have never worked on it before 3. The problem is familiar to you and you have worked on it before			

Rate the level of difficulty of the problem stated in the exercises? (from 1 = low and 3 = high)

PROBLEM	1	2	3
AP1			
IP1			

Elicitation and Conceptualization

Do you think you were given enough time for the elicitation process?

- Yes
 No

If not, explain why:

Do you think you were given enough time to write the requirements specification during the exercise?

- Yes
 No

If not, explain why:

Need of further interviews

In the first simulated interview, do you think that you understood the problem domain and identified the main requirements? If you think there were differences among problems, please give a brief explanation:

Do you think that more interactions with the customers (that is, more interviews) are necessary to understand the different problems? How many?

Thanks for taking this survey.